

INVESTIGATION OF THERMOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ABLATIVE THERMAL PROTECTIVE MATERIALS UNDER HIGH TEMPERATURE

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SUMMARY: In this paper, according to the analysis of the ablative mechanism of thermal protective materials under elevated temperature, the ablation-phase transformation properties and the thermomechanical behavior of the component materials are investigated by Eshelby equivalent inclusion method. Through the hypothesis of the statistical uniform distribution of the phases consist of solid products of thermodestruction at high temperatures and pores in the materials, the interaction among different phases by complicated internal physico-chemical processes in a matrix and fibers is considered. The exact relationship between the micro-structure and the macro-behavior for ablative thermal protective materials are expressed, and the numerical solution are also given. With the help of the model, the following high-temperature phenomena have been described: degradation of elastic moduli of the materials in heating, dependence of heat properties of the materials not only on temperature but also on duration of heating. Comparison of the theoretical and experimental results for typical ablative materials showed that the model allows one to forecast the thermomechanical characteristics of the materials with sufficient accuracy. It will be helpful for the analysis of the composite materials high-temperate structure.

KEYWORDS: Micromechanics, Thermal protective materials, Thermo-mechanical properties, Ablation, High temperature

INTRODUCTION

Investigation of ablation processes of composite materials plays an important role for many applied problems, in particular for designing a heat shield of re-entry vehicles. For example, heat-shield components of aeronautic engine will endure complex stresses, high temperatures of 1800-2500K and thermo-mechanical erosion of gas flow with a long period of 2000-3000 hours. The nozzle throat of the solid rocket motor works in the environment of ultra-high temperature and high-speed gas flow. Interaction of such heat-shield composite materials as carbon/phenolic, carbon/carbon, and ceramic matrix composites with a hot oxygen-containing gas flow is heterogeneous combustion. The ablation processes are usually divided into: volumetric ablation and surface ablation[1]. Volumetric ablation is a physico-chemical processes, which leads to decrease in density due to internal gas generation, but surface ablation causes decreasing geometrical dimensions of the structures.

The mechanical behaviours of composites at normal and elevated temperatures have already been studied in great detail. Most investigations of the high-temperature behaviour of composites have been only concerned with heat phenomena such as the rate of thermo-chemical ablation[2-8], changing heat conductivity and density, and calculation of the temperature field in the composite as a function of surface ablation[9-12]. On the other hand, some experimental and theoretical experience has been accumulated on thermal and physico-chemical ablation processes of composite materials under high temperatures. However, problems of macro- and micromechanics of composites at high temperatures, especially under the ablation conditions, have little previously been investigated[13-16]. The aim of the present paper is to model the thermo-mechanical behaviour of the ablative materials under high temperatures.

SOLVING THE VOLUMETRIC ABLATIVE PROBLEM

Composite materials under normal temperatures consist of two phases: reinforcing filler and polymer phase of matrix, between which there exist only mechanical interactions. Under high temperatures a polymer matrix ablates by pyrolysis and two new phases appear: pyrolytic phase containing solid products of decay (as a rule, carbon) and gas phase containing gaseous products of decomposition of the polymer, this gas phase occupies pores of the material. Fillers can ablate too (for example, if they are organic fibres); then another solid phase appears in the composite, conventionally called a 'crystalline' phase of the fibre, and pores filled with gas also appear in the fibre. The initial solid phase, the fiber was under normal temperature, is called 'amorphic' in this case. For organic fibres, the 'amorphic' phase is the initial polymer, and the 'crystalline' one is a pyrolytic residue, usually carbon. For carbon fibres, the 'amorphic' phase is amorphous or crystalline carbon and no essentially new solid phase appears under heating in an oxidizing medium, the fiber goes completely into a gas phase. Similar processes occur with boron fibres in oxidizing surrounding.

Besides mechanical interaction between the initial phases and new phases of matrix and filler, there is also a physico-chemical interaction: under the action of high temperatures, substances of 'old' solid phases pass gradually into 'new' phase states. This process is called ablation-phase transformation processes.

An ablating composite material is considered to be a multiphase system consisting of five phases, the geometrical shape of each phase is a certain finite domain V_i . This domain is not static, i.e. it changes with time $V_i = V_i(t)$ under the action of high temperatures, even without the presence of deformations, where $i=a$ (amorphous), b (polymer), l (crystalline), p (pyrolytic) and g (gas of pores). Fig.1 shows schematically a physical model of the change of an actual structure made of composite materials under high temperatures.

**Fig.1 A physical model of microstructure for porous medium at elevated temperature
(a) before and (b) after ablation**

Main assumptions for this study:

- a) Deformations of solid phases of the composite are small.
- b) The statistical uniform distribution of the phases consist of solid products of thermo-destruction at high temperatures and pores in the materials.
- c) The phases separation boundaries Σ_{ij} is smooth without corner points.
- d) Only the process of volumetric ablation by thermo-decomposition is considered, and the pyrolysis of composite material is simulated by parallel phase transformations of types $b \rightarrow p, a \rightarrow l$ and $a, b \rightarrow g$
- e) Each of the phase transformations is considered as a process of continuously decreasing and increasing volumes of the other phases, so that the total volume of the representative

cell does not change.

Supposing the volume of the representative cell is φ :

$$\varphi = \varphi_a + \varphi_b + \varphi_l + \varphi_p + \varphi_g \quad \text{Eqn.1}$$

Here φ_i is the volumetric content of the different phases.

Let $\varphi_f = \varphi_a + \varphi_l$ be the total volumetric part of the whole fibre in the composite, then we can derive the equation of changing mass of the fibers and matrix:

$$\rho_f \frac{d\varphi_f}{dt} = -J_f \Gamma_f \quad \text{Eqn.2}$$

$$\rho_b \frac{d\varphi_b}{dt} = -J_m \quad \rho_p \frac{d\varphi_p}{dt} = J_m (1 - \Gamma_m) \quad \text{Eqn.3}$$

Here ρ_f, ρ_b are densities of the fibers and the polymer phases of the matrix. Γ_f, Γ_m are the gasification coefficients of the fibers and matrix, J_f, J_m are the rates of volumetric ablation of the fiber and matrix, they describe heat-mass transfer intensity in thermo-destruction in accordance with Arrhenius's law:

$$J_f = J_f^0 \varphi_a \exp\left[-\frac{E_{Af}}{R\theta(t)}\right] \quad J_m = J_m^0 \varphi_b \exp\left[-\frac{E_{Am}}{R\theta(t)}\right] \quad \text{Eqn.4}$$

E_{Am} and E_{Af} are their activation energy, respectively, R is universal gas constant. J_f^0, J_m^0 are pre-exponential factors determined by experiments. $\theta(t)$ is temperature, may be supposed to be linear law with heating time, $\theta = \theta_0 + \theta' t$. $\theta_0 = 293\text{K}$ is normal temperature, θ' is heating rate.

As follows from the equation (2), the volumetric content of fibres changes due to gasification of the fibres under high temperatures. Volumetric contents of amorphous and crystalline phases of fibers are defined by function φ_f :

$$\varphi_a(t) = \frac{\varphi_f(t) - \varphi_f^0(1 - \Gamma_f)}{\Gamma_f} ; \quad \varphi_l(t) = \frac{1 - \Gamma_f}{\Gamma_f} [\varphi_f^0 - \varphi_f(t)] \quad \text{Eqn.5}$$

At the initial state under temperature $\theta_0 = 293\text{K}$, $\varphi_f = \varphi_f^0, \varphi_a = \varphi_f^0, \varphi_l = 0$, where φ_f^0 is the initial volumetric content of the fibre in the composite. Volumetric content φ_p of pyrolysis phase of the matrix is expressed analytically in terms of φ_b :

$$\varphi_p(t) = [\varphi_b^0 - \varphi_b(t)] \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_p} (1 - \Gamma_m) \quad \text{Eqn.6}$$

Here φ_b^0 is the initial volumetric content of the polymer phases.

Then from equations (2)-(4) one can derive the volumetric contents for the ablative composite materials:

$$\varphi_f(t) = (1 - \Gamma_f) \varphi_f^0 - \Gamma_f \varphi_f^0 \exp \int_0^t \frac{J_f^0}{\rho_f} \exp\left[-\frac{E_{Af}}{R\theta(\tau)}\right] d\tau \quad \text{Eqn.7}$$

$$\varphi_b(t) = \varphi_b^0 \exp \int_0^t -\frac{J_m^0}{\rho_b} \exp\left[-\frac{E_{Am}}{R\theta(\tau)}\right] d\tau \quad \text{Eqn.8}$$

MICROMECHANICAL MODEL OF THE ABLATIVE MATRIX AND FIBER

Fig.2 shows the statistical uniform distribution of the phases consist of solid products of thermo-destruction at high temperatures and pores in the material element. The solid phases

are viewed as spheroids and the pores as sphere voids.

Fig.2 Analytical model for a representative cell of the ablative matrix or fiber materials

(superscript old=*a, b*), the elastic modulus of the pyrolytic or crystalline phases C_{ijkl}^{new} (superscript new=*p, l*) is assumed to be independent of temperature, and they are assumed to be linearly isotropic. The elastic modulus of the polymer phase and amorphous phase essentially depends on temperature and duration of heating. To take account of the phenomenon playing an important role in calculations of stresses in structures, we use the following dependence (Reference [1]):

$$E^{old}(\theta, t) = E^0 a^{(0)}(\theta, t), \quad a^{(0)}(\theta, t) = \exp[(-a\Delta\hat{\theta})^r] \quad \text{Eqn.9}$$

Where $\Delta\hat{\theta} = \Delta\theta + P \int_0^t \exp[-Q(t-\tau)] \Delta\theta(\tau) d\tau$, $\Delta\theta = \theta - \theta_0$, E^0 is a value of the elastic modulus of the material in it's initial state at temperature $\theta_0 = 293K$, constants a , r and P , Q are evaluated in experiments. Values of the parameter depend on the type of ablative matrix and fiber. Generally, the constants P and Q can be considered as universal, i.e. they are the same for all ablative materials ($P = 1.56 \times 10^{-4} / s$, $Q = 2.5 \times 10^{-4} / s$). Value of r is usually equal to 1-3.

Under the applied stress σ_{ij}^0 the average of the total stress in the matrix or fiber can be given by the Eshelby equivalent inclusion method:

$$\langle \sigma_{ij}^{old} \rangle_{Matrix \text{ or } fiber} = C_{ijkl}^{old} (\varepsilon_{kl}^0 + \tilde{\varepsilon}_{kl}) \quad \text{Eqn.10}$$

In eq. (10) $\langle \rangle$ denotes the volume averaged quantity and $\tilde{\varepsilon}_{kl}$ denotes the average strain disturbance in the matrix due to all pyrolytic phases and pores, or in the fibers due to all crystalline phases. For the entire homogeneous domain without containing the inhomogeneities the following relation always holds, $\sigma_{ij}^0 = C_{ijkl}^{old} \varepsilon_{kl}^0$.

Now introduce inclusions consist of solid products of thermo-destruction at high temperatures and pores into the multiphase materials, then the equivalent inclusion method yields in the inhomogeneities:

$$\langle \sigma_{ij}^{new} \rangle_{matrix \text{ or } fiber} = C_{ijkl}^{new} (\varepsilon_{kl}^0 + \tilde{\varepsilon}_{kl} + \varepsilon_{kl}^1) = C_{ijkl}^{old} (\varepsilon_{kl}^0 + \tilde{\varepsilon}_{kl} + \varepsilon_{kl}^1 - \varepsilon_{kl}^*) \quad \text{Eqn.11}$$

$$\langle \sigma_{ij}^{gas} \rangle_{matrix \text{ or } fiber} = C_{ijkl}^{old} (\varepsilon_{kl}^0 + \tilde{\varepsilon}_{kl} + \varepsilon_{kl}^2 - \varepsilon_{kl}^{**}) = 0 \quad \text{Eqn.12}$$

where ε_{ij}^1 and ε_{ij}^2 are the disturbance of the strain due to this single inclusion, respectively. ε_{kl}^* , ε_{kl}^{**} are the corresponding equivalent eigenstrains which have non-vanishing components in the domain of this single inclusion, and become zero outside this inhomogeneities. Following Eshelby equivalent inclusion method, we have:

$$\varepsilon_{kl}^1 = S_{klmn}^1 \varepsilon_{mn}^* \quad \text{Eqn.13}$$

$$\varepsilon_{kl}^2 = S_{klmn}^2 \varepsilon_{mn}^{**} \quad \text{Eqn.14}$$

where S_{klmn}^1, S_{klmn}^2 are the 4-th order Eshelby's tensor for the equivalent inclusions which depends on C_{ijkl}^{old} and the geometry of the inhomogeneities. Since the stress is prescribed, the average of the disturbed stress in the matrix or fiber must vanish (Reference [17]), i.e.,

$$\langle \sigma_{ij}^0 \rangle = \varphi_{old} \langle \sigma_{ij}^{old} \rangle + \varphi_{new} \langle \sigma_{ij}^{new} \rangle + \varphi_g \langle \sigma_{ij}^{gas} \rangle \quad \text{Eqn.15}$$

For the matrix we have $\varphi_{old} = \varphi_b, \varphi_{new} = \varphi_p, \varphi_g = 1 - \varphi_b - \varphi_p$, and for the fiber $\varphi_{old} = \varphi_a, \varphi_{new} = \varphi_l, \varphi_g = 1 - \varphi_a - \varphi_l$. Eliminating $\varepsilon_{ij}^1, \varepsilon_{ij}^2$ through eqs. (13) and (14), we have three unknowns, i.e., $\tilde{\varepsilon}_{ij}, \varepsilon_{ij}^*$ and ε_{ij}^{**} , which will be solved by the three equations (eqs. (11), (12) and (15)). It is seen that as soon as the equivalent eigenstrains is determined properly, the average fields and overall elastic constants of the ablative materials are readily obtained.

The prediction of the effective (macroscopic) properties of composite materials has been studied extensively for composites reinforced with unidirectional continuous fibres. There are a total of five independent material constants in the matrix for transversely isotropic materials, and nine for orthotropic ones. The five independent elastic constants of unidirectional composite can also be expressed:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= \varphi_f E_f(t) + (1 - \varphi_f) E_m(t) \\ E_{22} &= E_m(t) E_f(t) / [\varphi_f E_m(t) + (1 - \varphi_f) E_f(t)] \\ G_{12} &= G_m(t) G_f(t) / [\varphi_f G_m(t) + (1 - \varphi_f) G_f(t)] \\ G_{23} &= G_m(t) / [1 - \varphi_f^{1/2} (1 - G_m(t) / G_f(t))] \\ \gamma_{12} &= \varphi_f \gamma_f + (1 - \varphi_f) \gamma_m \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eqn.16}$$

where subscripts f and m respect fiber and matrix, $i = 1, 2, 3$ are local coordinates for the considered fiber orientation.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Values of the parameters for ablative materials depend on the type of medium where heating of the material occurs: inert (vacuum, inert gas) or oxidizing (air, oxygen). In inert gas a process of thermo-decomposition (TD) of the material occurs; in an oxidizing environment there is thermo-oxidative decomposition (TOD). The thermo-mechanical characteristics of typical ablative materials (fibers and matrices) for TD and TOD processes are listed in table 1, respectively.

Table 1 The thermo-mechanical parameters of different ablative materials [1]

Characteristics of materials	Silicon organic matrix	Phenolic matrix	Epoxy matrix	Carbon fiber	Boron fiber	Organic fiber Kevlar-49
$\rho_{old} (\times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3)$	1.4	1.1	1.2	1.8	2.58	1.45
$\rho_{new} (\times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3)$	2.0	2.0	2.0	-	-	-
$a / \theta_0 (1/K)$	0.1	0.3	0.7	0.001	0.001	0.1

E^0 (GPa)	3.8	4.1	3.2	250.0	420.0	145.0
γ	0.35	0.35	0.37	0.21	0.2	0.3
E^{new}/E^0	0.01	1.0	0.3	1.3	0.1	0.3
J^0 ($\times 10^5$ kg/m ³ ·s)	5.0	3.3	3.6	0.0054	0.078	0.42
For TD and TOD E_A/R ($\times 10^3$ K)	10.5 10.3	9.0 8.7	7.8 7.5	7.0 6.5	12.0 9.5	9.0 8.6
For TD and TOD Γ	0.45 0.55	0.4 0.6	0.7 0.97	0.05 0.7	0.07 0.9	0.35 0.8

Fig. 3 Volume content of the initial and resultant phase materials of boron fiber versus temperature with heating rate 0.1K/s

Fig. 5 Dependence of elastic modulus of Phenolic matrix on temperature with different heating rates in air environment

Fig. 7 Dependences of shear modulus of boron-phenolic unidirectional composites on temperature

Fig. 4 Dependence of elastic modulus on temperature under heating with rate 0.1K/s in inert environment for different types of fibers

Fig. 6 Dependences of elastic modulus of boron-phenolic unidirectional composites on temperature

The curves of volume contents of initial and resultant phase of boron fiber versus temperature in air and vacuum environment are depicted in Fig.3. As temperature increasing, the volume content of initial phase reduces gradually, while the volume content of resultant phase increases and approaches to constant. The curves indicate that TOD of the material in air output more gas than TD in vacuum, the corresponding porosity is large also.

Fig.4 shows the dependences of elastic modulus of different fiber materials on temperature in the vacuum environment. The moduli of boron and Kevlar-49 fiber decrease slowly below the thermal decomposing temperature. As temperature exceed the thermal decomposing temperature, the moduli are mainly influenced by porous and phase-transformation. The elastic modulus of carbon fiber decreases in a non-monotonic rule about 1000oC-1200oC, as resultant phase are of higher graphitization, and the variation will backward with greater heating rate. The corresponding experimental data reported in Dimitrienko (1999) are also given in Fig.4.

The elastic modulus of phenolic resin change with heating rates are depicted in Fig.5 (curves are computations, points are experimental data). As temperature rising, the modulus has a light fluctuation before thermo-decomposing temperature reached. If the temperature is exceed the thermo-decomposing temperature, the modulus changes intensely as phase transformation appearance and gas occurs. The computed results are in a good agreement with experimental data reported in Dimitrienko (1999). Pyrolysis will carry out at higher temperature as material heated by larger heating rate.

The relations of elastic and shear modulus for boron/phenolic unidirectional composites to temperature under heating with rate 0.1K/s are given in Fig.6 and Fig.7. One can make the following conclusion from these results: degradation of elastic moduli of the unidirectional composite in the reinforcing direction in heating, simultaneously with degrading properties of its matrix and fibers.

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